

ISic4385

I.Sicily inscription 4385

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Ietas

Place of origin (modern)

Monte Iato

Provenance

Found in re-use in the north wall of a medieval house immediately north of the oikos temple in the area of the agora

Coordinates

37.966941, 13.198293

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Monte Iato, Monte Iato Excavation stores, inventory I 16 B

Physical Description

A fragmentary block of local grey limestone, of which part of the upper edge is preserved, but broken on all other sides

Dimensions

Height 41 cm

Width 54 cm

Depth 24 cm

Layout

Remains of two lines of Latin letters

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Plainly incised regular Latin capitals, with minimal serifs (but surface is badly worn); Q is slightly larger than the other letters at 120mm

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: 100-105 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. [---] Germa[nus---]

2. [---] praef(ectus)cohortis---] eq(uitatae) · t[rib] [(unus)mil(itum)leg(ionis)---]
undefined. [---]

Apparatus

Text of A. Kolbe in Mohr et al. 2018

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Mohr, M., Reusser, C., Kolb, A., Elsener, A. 2018. Forschungen auf dem Monte Iato 2017. *Antike Kunst*. 61: 88-107. At 100-101 tav.15.2

Mohr, M., Reusser, C., Elsener, A. 2017. Forschungen auf dem Monte Iato 2016. *Antike Kunst*. 60: 91-108. At 94-95

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